

Financial Indicators on Economic Growth: Evidence from Pakistani Financial Institution

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Abstract

Current research has analyzed impacts of financial development both short run and long run, on economic growth of Pakistan during the period 1980-2014. To measure financial development, study has utilized principal component analysis (PCA) to form a single proxy index that covers four important dimensions such as banking and non-banking financial institutions and both financial access and markets simultaneously. It consists of five financial development ratios e.g. financial system deposits to GDP, private sector credit of banks to GDP, commercial bank assets to commercial and central banks assets, foreign direct investments to GDP and financial market capitalization to GDP. Empirical findings suggest that long run relationship is more evident in case Pakistan's context for financial development and growth of an economy. While the mechanism of short run dis-equilibrium adjustment in case of estimated, error correction model is expected towards the long run relation. Policy makers can use results for parallel and successful expansion of both financial and economic development

Keywords: Financial Development, Financial Deepening & Financial Access. PCA, Pakistan

1. Introduction

Most of the time economy's growth is determined through production factor, however, the endogenous theories point out the "technological innovations" act as the backbones of the growth of an economy. Romer (1990), state financial development (FD) is a critical element of economics' growth after globalization. Financial development is mix of multiples aspects like financial liberalization, broadening and deepening, where former refers to elimination and deregularization of capital flow's restrictions once services especially financial ones are easily in use of end users. Whereas broadening is about in increase in institution's number and deepening is rise of assets financially. Thus to be precise, (Levine, 2007) proposes that FD plays an essential role in funds mobilization for speedy processes of units production especially in case of pooling from surplus units to deficits ones which all merges in country's economic growth.

Studies (Bagehot, 1873; Hicks, 1969; Lucas, 1988; Robinson, 1952; Shaw, 1973) indicates relation of economy's growth to FD from long-time advocating the perspective that for an country's economic growth its financial systems is very strong determinant which if effectively and efficiently managed can help to locate efficacious projects based on technological innovations. These concepts have motivated the developing countries especially, to improve the development of their financial systems so that their economic position may improve. For this purpose, extensive research is also done to clarify in various economies to clarify link of FD with growth of economy i.e. developing and developed nations. Literature quote on basis of empirical analysis shows a long-term relation exists between these aspects (Adu, Marbuah, & Mensah, 2013; Fama, 1990; Hye, 2011).

Despite of being a small economy, Pakistan plays important role on the screen on international trade and market. Since the time it got its independence, the economy has undergone drastic changes. It is an agriculture country but with the passage of time, significant financial development has taken place after phenomena of globalization and reforms of 1900s of financial liberalization have occurred.

No doubt, extensive research has tried to explain the scenario but FD's real measures are still unknown. Earlier researches (Rousseau & Wachtel, 1998; Khan, 2005) conducted worldwide including Pakistan have been built upon the utilizing a single variable for measurement of FD. These studies utilizing only one measure from banking segment only failed to depict true picture of overall financial development as findings were contradictory for different countries. In addition, multi co linearity found when multiple variables were employed and it was problematic (Adu et al. 2013). Therefore, Huang (2005) constructed one composite proxy in form of index for the first time who formally tried to examine financial development in detail with different dimensions. After that, some other studies also performed similar efforts to construct financial proxy for different economies (Ang & Mckibbin, 2007; Saci & Holden, 2008; Hye, 2011).

Some researchers of Pakistan have also tried to construct an index of financial development (Khan & Qayyum, 2007; Jalil & Faridun, 2011; Nabila, 2014) but these studies have also focused only banking sector as a crucial determinant of financial development and found almost similar results. So, they failed to depict comprehensive impacts of financial development with respect of its maximum dimensions. As no study agreed on any single proxy of financial development thus, more research is required to find a reliable and comprehensive financial development measure. Only then, relationship of FD and economy's growth could be examined correctly. Particularly for Pakistan, this topic is not investigated acceptably and current quantitative research is one effort to determine the actual determinant behind financial development. Current effort opens more horizons of research for policy makers and institutional managers so that they can take appropriate actions to stimulate economic growth.

Further discussion is organized in multiples sections, where section 2 & 3 develops theoretical foundations respective to endogenous growth theory and constructs in discussion. Section 4 constitutes model's empirical representation alongwith data used and employed methodology while section 5 elaborates empirical analysis and its effects. At the end of the study in section 6 conclusions are drawn and policy implications are also provided.

2. Theoretical Foundation

Classical growth theory in economics determines that factors of production increase the total output with constant technology. Time-consuming growth is established through saving proportion but rate of technical advancement and saving rate is not explained there. But endogenous growth theories suggest that growth of economy is conclusion of those internal aspects that are governing opportunities to innovations, skills, knowledge, human capital etc. And this theory has defined the channels through which economic variables affect technology, hence economic growth. It begins by adoption of innovation in production, processes and even markets. Thus economic policies of trade, taxes, subsidies, influence the adoption of innovations affecting cost and research and development expenditures of firms.

Current study is based on AK model that is humblest endogenous model that is not differentiating capital accumulation and technological innovation. AK theory suggests that an rise in saving rate determines higher long term economic development of an economy. It explains physical, and human capital together. It states that aggregate production function, Y is proportional to constant or increasing aggregate capital, K. This is due to fact that when firm have capital, it can be intellectual capital that is the result of technological innovations with no diminishing property of marginal capital.

$$Y = AK$$

Parameter A is a constant productivity factor explaining the impact of financial and technological progress (Romer, 1990) and K is the capital both physical and human.

After globalization, there are advancements in the process of flow of capital towards deficit production unit hence, nature of the abilities of labor and capital flow have changed according to technology innovations. Theoretical and empirical evidences confirm development of economy by means of a powerful energy behind development of economy.

3. Literature Review

Since financial reforms of time span of 1990, concept of monetary expansion and advancement of economy has attained significant importance for investigators and strategy maker. Several time series work has examined how financial development F.D and economic growth are related.(King and Levine, 1993) deliberated association of both for 80 sample economies for time period 1960-89. They measured FD with the proportion of liquefied accountabilities to Gross Domestic Production and economic growth by per capita real earnings level and found a highly significant relationship.

Demetriades and Hussein (1996) discovered monetary development and growth of economy of Nepal during time span of 1962-92. They concluded that financial repression was positively related with economic growth. Moreover, real per capita income of Nepal was found to be positively related with financial deepness and a negative association was found with the bank networks. This negative relation was due to inefficient role of financial intermediaries of weak financial system of Nepal. The relationship among monetary expansion and growth of economy in circumstance of Sri Lanka studied by Ghatak (1997) during 1950-87 and found increase in economic growth by interest rate and financial deepening.

Further research on financial development was extended by including stock market as a determinant as pointed by Levine and Zervos (1998). Future level of economic growth was explained by annual and quarterly variations of stock returns in many following studies as of Chen (1991), Fama (1981), Evans (2001), and Dothan (1986).

Bell and Rousseau (2001) investigated the financial condition of India by using vector error correction model (VECM)claiming that to a dynamic player in increasing the level of investments rather than promoting total productivity factor were financial institutions. Such a condition was due to evidence of factor accumulation.

Some studies found the mixed consequences although examining association of financial expansion and growth of economy. Asian economies including Pakistan were studied for time span 1950-97 to analyze the effect on economy's growth due to FD (Sinha & Macri, 2001). Their findings established that both dimensions were positively related as a highly significant impression of financial measures on real per capita income was found after regression in Pakistan, Sri Lanka, India and Malaysia. Results also revealed two way causal relationship for India and Malaysia, one way for Japan and Thailand and in case of Pakistan, Philippines and Korea, reverse causality was found. In addition, they also determined that poverty levels are encouraged in the absence of financial development as multiple steady state equilibrium may exist in this poor level of financial development. Rousseau and Vuthipadadorn (2005) selected 10 economies including Pakistan and studied the strength of monetary intermediaries in growth of economy for sample era of 1950-2000. VAR and VECM approaches were useful to regulate causation among financial and economic measures. A durable unidirectional association between financial expansion and investment level was found but financial expansion has a weak association through economy's growth.

The linkage of financial development of Pakistan to economic growth was also determined by using Autoregressive Distributed Lag Approach (ARDL) for time span 1971-2004 (Khan, 2005). Their findings determined a positive long-run relation of financial depth with economic growth but an insignificant and positive relationship was found in short run. Thus, the following analysis recommended that growth of economy of Pakistan is consequence of financial expansion. In following situation of South Eastern European states, the overall procedures and threats along with weakness of swift financial development were examined by Winkler (2009). He evidenced that when more financial banks are permissible to come in market to achieve financial deepening, goal of economic growth is not attained instead financial stability comes at stake.

The investigation on topic of financial expansion was contributed by Adu et al. (2013) when in case of Ghana, they investigated situation of financial expansion with relation to economic growth. They found that with the choice of proxy used for financial expansion, the growth of economy effects were changed. Moreover, they evidenced the problem of multi co linearity when financial proxies were used at a time in one model as private

sector credit and domestic credit were determined favorable while broad money to GDP was not helpful in determining economic growth.

Almost all these studies have measured financial development with respect to banking sector only that's why here is no undisputed estimation of monetary expansion. While measuring financial development some important dimensions of financial development must be included measure of financial development. Although some efforts are done in this regard but these are also measuring financial development with respect to banking sector only.

Virtually entire earlier researches in dissimilar states as well as Pakistan have consumed particular variable to quantify monetary expansion such as M2 to Gross Domestic Product, liquefied accountabilities, private segment credit and stock market capitalization to GDP, etc. (King & Levine, 1993; Rousseau & Wachtel, 1998; Khan, 2005). Nevertheless these distinct measures were not originate enough to present factual depiction of monetary expansion by means of these were expressing part of banking segment merely diverse results were studied from one country to others. Furthermore, difficulties of multi co linearity rises although consuming extra financial proxies at a time (Adu et al. 2013). Consequently, prerequisite of a distinct multiple estimation of monetary expansion was felt. It was Huang (2005) who for the primary level, formally endeavor to study monetary expansion in detail with different dimensions by creation of four monetary expansion directories alike FD for Banks, Stock, proficiency and magnitude to estimate overall monetary expansion. Subsequently, round about further investigators of industrialized realms also assembled a distinct substitution in type of monetary expansion directory (Ang & Mckibbin, 2007; Antzoulatos, 2008; Saci & Holden, 2008; Hye, 2011).

World Economic Forum (WEF) also contributed in this regard and published its first financial development report in 2008 which included seven dimensions to paradigm a multiple monetary expansion catalog designed for 62 countries as standard. According to WEF, financial development is broadly divided into three main categories of policy makers, financial intermediaries and financial access (Financial development report, 2012). When studying the recent literature about Pakistan about financial/monetary expansion index and its impression on growth, some researchers are found. As Khan and Qayyum (2007) suggested a positive impression of monetary policies on growth of economy of Pakistan in time series study measured FD with help of ratios such as deposit liabilities to GDP, total quantity of clearance dynasty to GDP, private segment tribute to GDP and stock market capitalization to GDP in an index form.

After that, Jalil and Faridun (2011) examined relationship of monetary expansion and growth over the time series data for 1975-2008. Three measures of banking sector as liquefied accountabilities to GDP, private sector credit to Gross Domestic Product and commercial bank resources to commercial and central bank possessions were employed to construct financial depth index. They also originate a long term co-integrated positive impact of monetary expansion on economic growth.

Most recently, for developing countries, a study by Nabila and Asgher (2014) was observed on panel data over time period of 1978-2012. They also included three indicators as ratio of M2 to Gross Domestic Product, bank domestic credit to Gross Domestic Product and the proportion of domestic tribute to private credit to Gross Domestic Product to estimate monetary progress. A long run association among monetary expansion and growth of economy was confirmed and panel co-integration tests found bidirectional causality but weak relationship was examined for developing countries.

It is concluded that almost all the literature especially in Pakistan failed to present the comprehensive depiction of monetary expansion with respect of its maximum dimensions as they have focused only banking sector as a crucial determinant of financial development and found almost similar results. As no one agreed on any single proxy of financial development thus, immobile here is requirement of extra effort and paradigm a multiple and

reliable deputation of monetary expansion enveloping many magnitudes of monetary expansion so that a momentous relationship of monetary expansion and growth of economy can be examined.

3. Model, Data and Research Methods

The theoretical framework of this analysis is elaborated in Figure 1 where influence of monetary expansion along with labor force and gross fixed capital formation on growth is determined. Current study is measuring financial development through Financial Development Index (FD Index), composed of four magnitudes of monetary expansion to construct a composite and more reliable proxy. These dimensions are banks and non-banks monetary organizations, monetary access and monetary markets.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

A proxy must comprise various financial determinants in order to determine overall financial development. Some important dimensions of FD are financial institutions, markets, instruments; financial deepening, financial access etc. and these are used individually in previous literature (Haung 2005, Saci & Holden 2008, Hye 2011, Jalil & Faridun 2011, Nabila 2014).

Empirical Model

This research is determining the relations between financial development and economic growth of Pakistan. This influence is captured by endogenous growth model ($Y = AK$), originally developed by Rebelo (1991) and employed by Pagano (1993). This model is also similar to Cobb- Douglas production function that is developed by Charles Cobbs and Paul Douglas (1928). This is actually the functional form of the production function. It estimates the relationship between two inputs, labor and capital, and the output produced with the help of these inputs (Pagano 1993, Khan 2007, Jalil & Faridun 2011, Hye 2011).

Below Equation 1 is describing the modified form of AK model

$$Y = \delta L^\theta K^\phi \tag{1}$$

Where RGDP is presented by Y while δ indicates the residual explains the influence of financial development index. θ and ϕ represent the partial elasticity of labor force (L) and capital (K) respectively. Equation 1 can be modified as follows:

$$\text{Log RGDP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Log FD Index} + \beta_2 \text{Log L} + \beta_3 \text{Log K} + \mu \tag{2}$$

In above equation

<i>RGDP</i>	<i>Real Gross Domestic Product</i>
<i>FD Index</i>	<i>Financial Development Index</i>
<i>L</i>	<i>Labor Force</i>

In this study, the expected signs of impact of FD index, K and L on real gross domestic product are positive (+) as already determined by Adu et al. 2013; Hye, 2011; Khan and Qayyum, 2007; Jalil and Faridun, 2011; Nabila, 2014 and others. Mckinnon (1973) revealed that financial depth and output level are positively related as equilibrium of money and capital enhance savings and ultimately economic growth. Shaw (1973) suggested that financial intermediaries stimulate investment that increase total output level. Financial development and real output were also found positively related (King & Levine, 1993; Khan, 2006).

The Data

Current study has collected all the data from World Development Indicators (WDI) for Pakistan during the sample era 1980-2014

Moreover, this study has included various variables from four main segments of financial developments that are Banking Institutions; Non-Banking Financial Institution, Financial markets; Financial Access (Financial Development Report, 2012). The indicators chosen from these dimensions are representing the depth, activity and effectiveness of all these four dimensions.

Table 1 explains below the description of indicators employed in this research

Table 1: Names and Details of Variables

Variables	Detail and definition
Dimension of Banking Institutions & Non-Banking Institution	
Financial system deposits to GDP (FSD)	All three deposits (time, demand and saving) of financial institutions and commercial banks as a percentage of GDP
Private sector credit to GDP (PCB)	Distributed private sector credit of commercial banks and other financial institutions as percentage of GDP
Commercial bank assets to commercial plus central bank assets (CBCBA)	Ratio of all assets of commercial banks to that of central bank
Financial access indicator	
Foreign direct investments to GDP (FDI)	This measure is total foreign direct investments to GDP
Financial market indicator	
Stock market capitalization to GDP (FMC)	Total market capitalization of all the listed companies as a percentage of GDP
Economic variables	
Labor force (L)	People of age 15 or above (both employed and unemployed), able to produce goods and services within an specific time period
Gross fixed capital formation (K)	It included total investment in the country in the form of assets like land, buildings, machinery, equipment, roads, hospitals, railway lines etc.
Real gross domestic product (RGDP)	GDP can be defined as total number of goods and services produced in a country during a period of one year by residents only

Banking and Non-Banking Financial Institutions Indicators

Here, three ratios are employed to measure the financial depth, activity and expansion of both banking and non-banking sector of financial system. The variable of financial deposits to GDP is used to determine financial depth and liquidity position (Beck et al. 2000, Haung 2005 Nabila 2014). The measure of private sector credit of banks to GDP is employed to check the activity of financial intermediaries here as used by Levine and Zervos, 1998; Haung, 2005; Khan, 2007 and the expansion of financial intermediaries is determined with the help of the ratio of commercial bank assets to commercial plus central bank assets (King & Levine 1993, Haung 2005, Hye 2011, Jalil 2011, and Financial Development Report 2012).

Financial Market Indicators

Financial markets are also playing a very dynamic role in overall financial development of Pakistan therefore, the current study has also included the overall size aspect of financial markets in financial development. Previously this dimension is not properly employed.

This research is focusing only on the financial market size of Pakistan being the only developed financial market. For this purpose, the indicator of total stock market capitalization as a percentage of GDP is included to determine the size of stock market (Khan & Qayyum, 2007).

Financial Access Indicators

Financial access is another integral dimension of financial development (Financial Development Report, 2012). This is also included in the current study because the measures of size, activity and depth of financial sector does not assure whether financial services are in the access of end users or not.

Current study is capturing the impact of financial access by including the ratio of foreign direct investments to GDP (Financial Development Report, 2012) that comes under the category of commercial access. The role of financial access is determined for financial development in broad term than micro level impacts of number of ATMs and other retail access factors.

Total investment levels of a country are enhanced by level of foreign direct investments. Moreover, a positive impact of FDI on the economic growth of almost all economies especially in developing economies like Pakistan is found. The production abilities are also increased due to greater proportion of FDI as it achieves the benefits of investment in host country like technological and management transmission.

In the current study, along with financial development indicators, some economic variable like Real gross domestic product, Labor force and Gross fixed capital are used to verify the relationship as per empirical model of the study in equation 2. Current study has calculated real GDP when the nominal GDP is divided to consumer price index (CPI) considering CPI of 2000 as 100. GFCF and RGDP are adjusted for the year ended 1999-00.

Research Methodology

First and foremost, the technique of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) developed by Karl Pearson (1901) has helped to construct index for financial development measurement. PCA is used as the indexation technique because it overcomes the problems of multi co linearity and produce highly uncorrelated orthogonal components that exhibit maximum variation in the data (Jackson, 1991). Augmented Dicky Fuller unit root test is used to check the data stationary and Johansen co integration test developed by Johansen and Juselius (1998, 1990) has determined the long run relationship. Moreover, error correction model has also explained short run adjustments of variable in the long run.

5. Empirical Results and Findings

To construct a composite proxy for financial development, five indicators in technique of Principal Component Analysis are used that determined overall impact of financial development; stock market capitalization (all listed companies) to GDP. Private sector credit as a percentage of GDP, financial system deposits as a percentage of GDP, commercial banks assets with respect to commercial and central bank assets and finally ratio of FDI to GDP

Following formula is the case of financial development index

$$FD\ Index = \alpha_0A + \alpha_1B + \alpha_2C + \alpha_3D + \alpha_4E$$

In above equation, the original values of all five financial indicators; PCB, FSD, FMC, FDI and CBCBA are explained by A, B, C, D and E respectively while the loads of all financial indicators, obtained by the principal component analysis, are denoted by parameters $\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4$. The values and signs of these loads play a significant role to construct FD Index. The parameters are expected to have positive values as financial development indicators also effect economic growth positively (Levine 2007, Adu et al. 2013).

Then, degree of association among all indicators is measured with the help of correlation test. The direction and magnitude of relationship is depicted by sign and value. The results of correlation matrix are shown below.

Table 2 Correlation

	GFCF	FSD	FMC	FDI	CBCBA	PCB	RGDP	L
GFCF	1.000000							
FSD	0.628259	1.000000						
FMC	0.511922	0.157567	1.000000					
FDI	0.674984	0.488462	0.510919	1.000000				
CBCBA	0.816481	0.659450	0.554631	0.726961	1.000000			
PCB	0.487319	0.582580	0.045533	0.257282	0.350876	1.000000		
RGDP	0.907063	0.628580	0.491740	0.444143	0.777195	0.369804	1.000000	
L	0.903950	0.656703	0.493685	0.450322	0.782580	0.390764	0.996346	1.000000

Table 2 verifies that all five financial indicators PCB, FSD, FMC, CBCBA and FDI, have high positive and significant correlation among themselves and with RGDP also. So, there arises the doubt of problems of multi co linearity. Therefore, PCA is the most appropriate to build a composite index. PCA overcomes the effects of multi co linearity. Moreover, principal component analysis helps to utilize the information extracted from all the included indicators because high levels of correlation do not allow including more than one proxy of financial development in an equation at one time. It is also clear that these financial measures are most appropriate combination to obtain a proxy index of overall financial development due to high correlation values.

As PCA is used for the composite index construction so its findings presented in Table 3 reveal the five principal components PC1, PC2, PC3, PC4, PC5 through Eigen values and eigenvectors. The sum of cumulative proportion of these five variables is one. It can be concluded that PC1 explains 56 percent of total variance in the original data thus first principal component is retaining 56% of total information and reducing dimensionality of 56% as well. The second principal component reveals 23%, third 9 %, fourth 6% and last PC5 describes 3 % of overall standardized variance. Thus, the highest variation is enlightened by PC1 and FD index is calculated with the help of its value.

A positive coefficient value of factor loadings (eigenvectors) that is greater than 0.3 is considered significant. While observing the factor coefficients of first principal component (PC 1), it is noticed that individual contribution of PCB, FSD, FMC, FDI, and CBCBA to the total standardized variation of first principal component is 33%, 47%, 35%, 49% and 54% respectively. Financial development index is calculated when the weighted value of every financial variable is multiplied to their parameters

Table 3 Principal Component Analysis

Number	Eigenvalues: (Sum = 5, Average = 1)		Proportion	Cumulative Value	Cumulative Proportion
	Value	Difference			
1	2.809680	1.643229	0.5619	2.809680	0.5619
2	1.166451	0.670568	0.2333	3.976130	0.7952
3	0.495882	0.153731	0.0992	4.472013	0.8944
4	0.342152	0.156316	0.0684	4.814164	0.9628
5	0.185836	---	0.0372	5.000000	1.0000

Variable	Eigenvectors (loadings):				
	PC 1	PC 2	PC 3	PC 4	PC 5
PCB	0.336027	0.626465	0.616149	0.313262	-0.129830
FSD	0.470517	0.409254	-0.309415	-0.501770	0.513434
FMC	0.355442	-0.604752	0.606904	-0.250814	0.276938
FDI	0.493580	-0.241286	-0.340793	0.723579	0.241771
CBCBA	0.543820	-0.126920	-0.200376	-0.252229	-0.764449

When other principal components are examined, it is seen that factor loading values of FMC, FDI and CBCBA are negative and these are also less than 0.3. Thus only PC 1 is included for further calculations of FD index.

Financial Development Index (FD Index)

Figure 2 is reporting the annual behavior for financial developing index during the study period.

FD index has peak value of 90.73 in year 2006. This is because of the highest level of financial market capitalization during this year along with maximum value of ratio of foreign direct investment to GDP. It is evident from above graph that FDI of Pakistan is still very low due to lack of political stability, unsatisfied implementation of law and order and particularly of terrorism situation in the country especially in Karachi that is the active port of our country.

Figure 2: Financial Development Index

Moreover, inconsistent economic policies and discouraging attitude of government have also demotivated foreign investors to put their investments in Pakistan. Unproductive and prolonged complicated labor laws have frightened fruitful investment projects. Insufficient business environment and lack of infrastructure facilities especially electricity and gas, have also discouraged foreign investors to initiate investments in Pakistan. This FDI can surely increase the financial market activities as well as capitalization.

Unit Root Test

Before moving towards other techniques, the statistical properties of all data are checked by unit root test (Augmented Dicky Fuller test, ADF) to test the data stationary.

Table 4 Unit Root Test-Augmented Dicky fuller

At level			
Variables	K (lag)	ADF	DECISION
Log RGDP	0	-1.916052	Non-stationery
Log GFCF	1	-2.110087	Non-stationery
Log FD Index	0	-1.503419	Non-stationery
Log L	0	-0.115834	Non-stationery
At first difference			
Δ Log RGDP	0	-4.19537**	Stationery
Δ Log GFCF	0	-3.60158***	Stationery
Δ Log FD Index	0	-4.88896***	Stationery
Δ Log L	0	-5.71212***	Stationery

Note: *** and ** represent rejection of null hypothesis (series having unit root) at 1% and 5% level of significance.

The above results showed the presence of unit root in all series at level and hypothesis of no unit root is accepted. Thus, all the series are non-stationary at level. But all the variables are stationary in their first difference form, implying that all the data series are integrated of same order.

Johansen Co integration Test

After confirming the stationary of data series, co integration has determined the relationship of financial development and economic growth in the long run. As all the indicators of this study are integrated of same order, thus Johansen co integration test developed by Johansen (1988) and Johansen and Juselius (1990) is appropriate to apply.

From the result of Johansen co integration test in Table 5, the rejection of null hypothesis of no co integration is evident as the trace statistic and Eigen values are more than critical value of 0.05. Prob. Value is also less than 0.05. In other words, there is co integration among all the variables at 5% level of significance. Thus, there is existence of long run relationship between financial development and economic growth of Pakistan.

Table 5 Johansen Cointegration Test

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.637504	62.79016	54.07904	0.0069
At most 1	0.458537	29.30372	35.19275	0.1878
At most 2	0.150487	9.058886	20.26184	0.7308
At most 3	0.105436	3.676829	9.164546	0.4624

Trace test indicates 1 cointegrating eq. (s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	Critical 0.05Value	Prob.**
None *	0.637504	33.48644	28.58808	0.0108
At most 1	0.458537	20.24484	22.29962	0.0944
At most 2	0.150487	5.382056	15.89210	0.8530
At most 3	0.105436	3.676829	9.164546	0.4624

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 1 cointegrating eq. (s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Long Run Coefficients

From table 6, the coefficient of Log FDINDEX is found as 0.4852 meaning that one unit rise in financial development cause RGDP to increase by 0.48 percent. So financial development has a significant impact of 48% on economic growth of Pakistan and current findings are claiming the fact that a composite index is covering maximum picture of financial system.

Table 6 Long Run Coefficients

Variables	Dependent variable (Ln RGDP) coefficient	t-statistics
Ln FD INDEX	0.4852	2.0906
Ln GFCF	0.3666	3.6470
Ln LABOR	1.2058	11.1296

Economic growth in the long run is positively related with labor and capital. Current study has also revealed a remarkable positive influence of labor force upon economic growth. It is said that with one percent rise in labor force, real GDP increase by 1.20% while a 0.36% increase occur in RGDP due to gross investment. Thus, these two are also robust determinants of economic growth.

Current finding have also confirmed former literature result as of Barro (1991), King and Levine (1993), Beck et al. (2000), Arshad and Qayyum (2007) Adu et al. (2013), Nabila and Zakir (2014) Jalil and Faridun (2011).

Error Correction Model

Among variables, long run relationship can be seen that shows the presence of error correction model (ECM) which will help to understand the adjustments in short run towards long run by approach of error correction term.

Table 7 Error Correction Model
Dependent variable = D (Log RGDP)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EC (-1)	-0.225470	0.039724	-5.675890	0.0000
Log FD INDEX	0.180645	0.055765	3.239399	0.0033
Log GFCF	0.159855	0.044677	3.577978	0.0014
Lagged dependent variable	-0.195045	0.184352	-1.058008	0.2998
Lagged FD index	-0.019694	0.052015	-0.378615	0.7080
Lagged labor	-0.040475	0.133285	-0.303675	0.7638
Lagged GFCF	-0.075909	0.041352	-1.835677	0.0779
R-squared	0.535383	Mean dependent var	0.049926	
Adjusted R-squared	0.428164	S.D. dependent var	0.017816	
S.E. of regression	0.013473	Akaike info criterion	-5.590494	
Sum squared resid	0.004719	Schwarz criterion	-5.273053	
Log likelihood	99.24315	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-5.483685	
Durbin-Watson stat	1.786143			

The results obtained from ECM in Table 7 showed that error correction term is negative in sign and statistically significant. Its value reveals 22% deviation in long run real GDP adjustment in the current year. In addition, current study has found significant financial development index and affecting positively the economic growth of Pakistan in short run period as well. But, the lagged value of FD index, K and L are found negative in ECM. Thus in the short run, these are not related to one another as they were found in long run. These findings are also in line with Adu et al. (2013), Jalil and Faridun (2011) etc. The R² score of model also explains the fitness of model.

Stability test

Diagnostic and stability test of CUSUM and CUSUMSQ (Brown, Durbin, Evans, 1975) are also conducted to find out parameters instability. According to the findings given by these plots, all the data is stable and exist between critical boundaries of 5 % significance level. Thus, financial development and economic growth are strongly associated

Figure 3 (a) Plot of Cumulative Sum of Recursive Residuals

Figure 3 (b) Plot of Cumulative Sum of Square of Recursive Residuals

6. Conclusion and Policy Implication

The present study has analyzed relationship of financial development of Pakistan along financial access and deepening with economic growth. The findings revealed significant positive impact of financial development on Pakistan's economic growth. Major contribution of this study is the construction of composite proxy of financial development index by using five indicators of financial development with technique of PCA. This proxy is providing a detailed picture of financial development

These effects indicate that financial access can never be ignored along with the role of financial intermediaries which are helpful in the flow of capital and financial markets are ensuring liquidity by providing diversified portfolios. Thus, development of financial sector of Pakistan is one right way to stimulate the economy by formulating and adopting short run and long run policies. In this way policy makers are also recommended to accelerate the credit flow towards private firms of rural areas for optimum economic growth. Strong legal

atmosphere should be created for securing the rights of creditors then there will be transparent and fast transfer of credit. Moreover, as the stock exchange of Pakistan is considered as the important medium and long term investment opportunity so its efficiency and proper functioning should be ensured. Political stability if maintained will also attract foreign direct investments and its continuous increase will encourage development projects along with financial openness. On the whole, only a well-organized and effective financial system can lead not only Pakistan but also all developing economies towards the road of economic stability and growth indeed.

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